

Synthesis, Characterization and Thermal Properties of Novel Epoxy/ Expandable Graphite Composites

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ABSTRACT

Novel epoxy/EG composite were prepared successfully via the sol-gel method. Expandable graphite has been functionalized by IPTS using XPS to characterize. The silane function groups have been attached on the surface of EG, and they can proceed the sol-gel reaction to form the covalent bonds between epoxy and EG. The results of TGA of composites showed that functionalized EG can enhance the thermal stability of composites. TGA/MS shows that the inorganic components could suppress the production of toxic gases. The composite materials could provide a safer choice.

Keywords: Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs) ; Thermal properties ; Thermogravimetric analysis(TGA) ; Sol-gel methods

1. Introduction

Epoxy resins are widely used as coating, adhesives, primers, semiconductor encapsulation and as matrices for advanced fibre-reinforced composites [1]. A further requirement that has recently gained importance is the requirement of flame resistance and imparting flame retardance into epoxy resins has attracted much attention [2-4].

Expandable graphite (EG) which is a new generation of intumescent additives can provide the excellent flame retardancy to polymer matrixes. EG is a kind of exfoliated expanding particles that have been treated with an agent (H_2SO_4) that intercalates into the crystal structure of the graphite. The intercalated graphite under heat source can expand in the direction perpendicular to the carbons layers in the crystal structure [5].

Recent researches into the flame retardancy of EG have demonstrated that EG can improve flame-retardant property of coatings [6-8]. Due to poor compatibility between polymer matrix and expandable graphite, the performance of flame retardant will be

abated. In this study, expandable graphite was functionalized by coupling agent for increasing the interaction force between organic and inorganic phases. The covalent bonds were formed through sol-gel reaction. This will enhance thermal stability of composites. The structures of functionalized expandable graphite will be characterized by XPS. Thermal stability of composites will be discussed by TGA · IPDT, respectively. TGA/MS was used to analyze the gas products during the thermal degradation.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

The epoxy resin used was the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DEGBA, NPEL-128) which was generously provided by Nan Ya Plastics Corporation, Taiwan. Expandable graphite (EG) was supplied by Inter. Carbide Tech. Co. 3-Isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane (IPTS) as a coupling agent between epoxy resin and expandable graphite was purchased from the United Chemical Technologies, Inc., U.S.A. 4, 4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (DDM) as curing agent for epoxy monomer was purchased from the Acros Organics Co. Geel West Zone 2, Janssen Pharmaceuticaaan 3a, 2440 Geel, Belgium. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was reagent grade and supplied by the Echo Chemical Co. Ltd., Taiwan. Concentrated hydrochloric acid used was obtained from the Union Chemical Works Ltd, Taiwan.

2.2 Preparation of IPTS grafted EG (IPTS-EG)

In order to prepare IPTS-EG, 1 g EG was functionalized with 5 g IPTS in the presence of THF, as a solvent, at 60 °C for 4 hours. The reaction was monitored by FTIR. IPTS-EG was washed by anhydrous THF for several times, and then vacuum dried at room temperature overnight.

2.3 Preparation of Epoxy /IPTS-EG composites

The modified epoxy resin was synthesized as follows: 4g IPTS (equivalent weight 247g) was added to 10g DGEBA type epoxy resin(equivalent weight 180g) at 60°C, and was then stirred for 4 hours until the characteristic peak of the NCO group disappeared. IPTS reacted with epoxy to form IPTS-Epoxy. Adequate amounts of IPTS-EG were fed into a THF solution of modified epoxy and the final solution was stirred mechanically at room temperature for 20 minutes. The products were cast into aluminum dishes to gel at room temperature. The wet gels were aged at room temperature for 24 hours, and were then dried at 100 °C for 5 hours in a vacuum oven.

2.4 Reaction schemes

The novel composites materials were prepared as described in scheme 1 :

3. Results and Discussions

In this study, we prepare the organic/inorganic composite. Epoxy resin is the organic matrix and expandable graphite is the inorganic additive. Epoxy resin is a kind of thermoset polymer. Epoxy is composed of monomer and curing agent. 4, 4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (DDM) is the curing agent for epoxy monomer. DDM have $-NH$ functional group to react with the oxirane functional group of Epoxy monomers. This chemical reaction can form the 3-D network of organic matrix. IPTS is used as a coupling agent between organic and inorganic phases to enhance the compatibility through the sol-gel reaction. The modified epoxy which has the $-OEt$ functional group can react with the grafted EG that possesses $-OEt$ functional group through the sol-gel reaction.

3.1 FTIR of grafting reaction

Figure 1 presents FT-IR spectra of the reaction between epoxy and IPTS. The figure shows the disappearance of the characteristic peak of the NCO group of IPTS at 2270cm^{-1} . New characteristic peaks at 3400cm^{-1} and 1700cm^{-1} generated. The peaks represent the urethane linkages were formed. This phenomenon revealed that $-OH$ functional group of epoxy has reacted with $-NCO$ functional group of IPTS. The absorption peak around 1100cm^{-1} corresponding to $-OEt$ functional group of IPTS was observed after the reaction with IPTS and Epoxy. The absorption peak at 910cm^{-1} corresponding to oxirane group decreases with increasing the time of the cure reaction. After the reaction, epoxy resin possesses the functional group of $-OEt$ to proceed the sol-gel reaction. This can enhance the compatibility between organic and inorganic components.

3.2 XPS of functionalized reaction between IPTS and EG

XPS can be used as a tool to identify the linkage between the coupling agent and the inorganic filler. Figure 2(a) presents C1s XPS of EG. From the picture, there are five bonds which are C-O (286.3eV)、C=O (287eV) [24]、C-C/C-H (285.0eV)、C=C (284.4) [9]. Figure 3(b) shows C1s XPS of IPTS-EG and two new bonds formed, which are C-N (286.03eV) and C-Si(284.6eV) [9]. Figure 3 shows Si2p XPS spectrum of IPTS-EG. The picture present that the main bonding is C-SiO₃ (102.6eV) [10]. It means that C-Si-(OEt)₃ of IPTS have attached on the surface of EG. The evidences present that EG have been functionalized by NCO function group of IPTS.

3.3 Thermal Properties of Epoxy/EG composite

The TGA and DTG curves of Epoxy/EG composites are reported in Figure 4 and Figure 5 at 10 °C/min under nitrogen atmosphere. Table 1 presents the thermal property of the Epoxy resin with various contents of EG. Pure Epoxy shows two stage of thermal degradation. Epoxy/EG composites show two stages of weight loss: the first step takes place from about 150 to 360°C, the second one which occurs from 360 to 530 °C may be attributed to the degradation of residual material. The composites show lower weight loss rate and higher char residue at 800 °C than pure Epoxy. The char residue increase with the increase of EG contents. The maximum temperatures (T_m) of the first derivative weight loss curves for composites were shifted to higher temperatures than that of Epoxy. It means EG could enhance the thermal stability of Epoxy and retard the pyrolysis of resin.

From Table 1, the temperature of weight loss 10wt % (T_{d10}) for pure epoxy is 355 °C, while those of epoxy/EG are lower than 355 °C. That may be attributed to the thermal degradation of EG. EG begins to degrade at 213 °C and its T_m is 264 °C. EG is a synthesized intercalation compound that exfoliates when it is heated. The EG structure consists of layers of hexagonal carbon structures within which a chemical compound (H_2SO_4) can be intercalated. The chemical reaction of formation of EG is expressed as follows [11]:

According to Camino et al. [26], the expansion of EG is due to a redox process between H_2SO_4 and the graphite that originates the blowing gases according to the reaction:

The blowing effect causes an increase of the volume of the materials by about 300 times on heating above 200 °C. The gases escape through the edges of the graphite particles which lead to their irreversible expansion. The expanded graphite flakes will protect the resin from fire attacking.

3.4 Thermal Stability of Composite

The integral procedural decomposition temperature (IPDT) proposed by Doyle [12] involves the volatile parts of the polymeric materials and is used to estimate the inherent thermal stability of the polymeric materials [13-14]. From Table 1, the IPDT of pure epoxy was 640 °C and the IPDTs of composites were higher than that of pure epoxy. The thermal stability of the composites increased with the inorganic content. The inorganic components improve the thermal stability of pure epoxy.

3.5 TGA/MS of Composite

TGA/MS was used to analyze the gas products during the thermal degradation. The toxic gases are dangerous to the people in the fire accident. Figure 6 showed 3D TGA/MS spectrum of gas phase in thermal degradation of (a) pure epoxy (b) epoxy/EG30 composite at heating rate $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in helium atmosphere. From these spectra, the gas products of pure epoxy are different from the composite. This implied that the mechanism of degradation for pure epoxy is different from that of composite. The peak numbers of the composites were reduced dramatically, indicating that the resulting products were also reduced in the thermal degradation. Intensity of peaks is an indication of the quantities of the pyrolyzed products. The decrease of the pyrolysis products also indicate that the presence of EG strongly restrains the generation of flammable products of pyrolysis and hence retards the fire expansion.

Figure 7 showed ion current vs. temperature for C_6H_6 which is major toxic gas during thermal degradation. The main chains of epoxy have benzene rings structure. When the materials containing epoxy resin are placed in high temperature atmosphere, the materials will degrade and produce C_6H_6 toxic gases. From this picture, the area under the curve represents the amount of gas released. The benzene rings structures of composites containing EG are more stable than those of pure epoxy resin under high temperature atmosphere. The amount of toxic gases which were liberated from composite was much less than that from pure epoxy. The inorganic components could suppress the production of toxic gases. It is very important to survive for human being during the fire accident because the composites containing EG can degrade into toxic gases. The composite materials could provide a safer choice.

4. Conclusions

Novel epoxy/EG composite were prepared successfully via the sol-gel method. Expandable graphite has been functionalized by IPTS using XPS to characterize. The silane function groups have been attached on the surface of EG, and they can proceed the sol-gel reaction to form the covalent bonds between epoxy and EG. The results of TGA, IPDT of composites showed that functionalized EG can enhance the thermal stability of composites. TGA/MS shows that the inorganic components could suppress the production of toxic gases. The composite materials could provide a safer choice.

Figure 1 FTIR of the Reaction between epoxy and IPTS

Figure 2(a) C1sXPS of EG

Figure 2(b) C1sXPS of IPTS-EG

Figure 3 Si 2p XPS of IPTS-EG

Figure 4 TGA thermogram curves of Pure Epoxy with various EG contents

Figure 5 Derivative curves of Pure Epoxy with various EG contents

Figure 6 (a) 3D TGA/MS Spectrum of gas phase in thermal degradation of Pure Epoxy at heating rate 10°C/min

Figure 6 (b) 3D TGA/MS Spectrum of gas phase in thermal degradation of Epoxy/EG30 composite at heating rate 10°C/min

Figure 7 Ion current vs. temperature for C_6H_6

Scheme 1 Composite of IPTS-Epoxy and IPTS-EG

Table 1 The thermal property of the Epoxy resin with various contents of EG

SAMPLE NO.	IPDT (°C)	T _m (°C)		Td ₁₀ (°C)	Char yield at 800°C (%)
		1st	2st		
Pure Epoxy	640	242	403	355	15
Epoxy/EG10	767	305	436	265	30
Epoxy/EG20	1031	302	438	303	35
Epoxy/EG30	1289	263	413	246	40

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